

Report on guidelines for a conscientious use of SSL luminaires at art exhibitions

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In the EMRP Joint Research Project (JRP) "Metrology for Solid State Lighting", the following partners cooperate to create a European infrastructure for the traceable measurement of solid state lighting: VSL (Coordinator), Aalto, CMI, CSIC, EJPD, INRIM, IPQ, LNE, MKEH, NPL, PTB, SMU, SP, Trescal, CCR, TU Ilmenau and Université Paul Sabatier. See <http://www.m4ssl.npl.co.uk/> for more information.

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SUMMARY

Works of art lighting represents a difficult task of balancing two different and opposite aspects: perception that requires adequate levels of light, and conservation that needs absence of radiation.

Perceptual features require the evaluation of several aspects of the exposition, not only linked to lighting conditions, as:

- artefact position with respect to visitor, others works of art and luminaires or windows;
- background dimension and colour;
- illumination level and uniformity on the object surface and in the room;
- light modelling;
- glare due to direct light from luminaires or windows or due to light reflected by the artefact surface or protective objects like glass units;
- spectral properties of the light .

Works of art conservation is aimed to the minimization of degradation of materials that can be achieved with the control of environmental parameters, like temperature, humidity, pollutions and light.

Light can degrade materials by thermal effect (the lighted surface is heated by radiations) or by photochemical effects (chemical transformation activated by the radiation energy). These effects depend on the level of radiation in short period or from the total energy incident on the artefact (radiant exposure or dose). The sensibility to wavelength depends on the type of material and it is not constant.

The use of SSL in lighting installations for museums and expositions is increasing for their low level of UV and IR radiation, the relatively high luminous efficacy that reduces the thermal load, the wide range of correlated colour temperature and good colour perception properties, the small dimensions of luminaires and the possibilities to obtain peculiar luminous intensity distribution.

Current requirements for lighting conditions standards do not consider peculiarities of SSL sources. Lighting levels or colour rendering indexes defined in the past considering traditional light source could be completely or partially not applicable with SSL source.

This report analyses two main problems: the fading effect of SSL sources compared to traditional ones and the low reliability of general colour rendering indexes when applied in work of art lighting.

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LIST OF SYMBOLS

ΔE	difference between 2 colour stimuli defined as the Euclidean distance between the points representing them in the CIE $L^*a^*b^*$ space. Dimension 1.
GAI_{REF}	gamut area index for the CIE 15 reference colour samples. Dimension 1.
GAI_{EXT}	gamut area index for 64 colour samples. Dimension 1.
R_a	general colour rendering index for the CIE 8 reference colour samples. Dimension 1.
R_{all}	general colour rendering index for the CIE 15 reference colour samples. Dimension 1.
R_{dye}	general colour rendering index for the 49 works of art selected dyes. Dimension 1.
R_{ext}	general colour rendering index for 64 colour samples. Dimension 1.
R_i	special colour rendering index. Dimension 1.
T_{cp}	correlated colour temperature, in kelvin.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ANSI	American National Standards Institute
BSI	British Standards Institution
BWS	Blue Wool Standard
CCT	Correlated Colour Temperature
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CIE	Commission Internationale de l'Eclairage
CRI	Colour Rendering Index
DM	Decreto Ministeriale (Italian Decree Law)
EMRP	European Metrology Research Programme
EN	European Standard
GAI	Gamut Area Index
IESNA	Illuminating Engineering Society of North America
IR	Infrared

ISO	International Organization for Standardization
JRP	Joint Research Project
LED	Lighting Emitting Diode
NIR	Near Infrared (radiation from 0,75–1,4 μm)
NMI	National Measurement Institute
n.p.	not provided
PAS	Publicly Available Specification
SSL	Solid State Lighting
UV	Ultraviolet
UV-A	Ultraviolet radiation from 315 nm to 400 nm
UNI	Ente Nazionale Italiano di Unificazione (Italian Standard Organization)
VIS	Visible spectrum

1 INTRODUCTION

Works of art lighting represents a difficult exercise of balancing two different and opposite aspects: perception and conservation.

The choice of a light source and of the lighting installation layout must follow basic principles for:

- minimizing degradation of materials;
- increasing colour perception conditions;
- creating acceptable conditions for the visibility of details (contrast);
- operating in agreement with international and/or national recommendation for conservation (limitation of illuminance levels and exposure, thermal load, UV radiation);
- improving the enjoyment of the exposition.

The appearance and the visual perception of a work of art surface are the key parameters to evaluate the efficacious of a lighting installation in creating smart and amazing display. The correct perception of colours, maintaining their harmony as thought by the artist, increases the enjoyment that people go through with during the museum visit.

Light always create damage. Variation of surface colours (perceived and/or measured) could be an early indicator of conservation problems too. Especially for the more sensitive materials, damage can be slowed down using appropriates levels and conditions of lighting but cannot completely avoided.

Several guidelines and standards have been published on this topic [1] [2] [3] [4] [5] [6] [7] [8] [9]. These documents usually focus more attention on conservation requirements rather than perceptive aspects; in several cases specifications about environmental parameters control (in terms of temperature, humidity and pollutants) are also included. Only few of them consider the whole management of collections, including not only rules for display but also for transport, rental, monitoring ...

None of the available documents specifies peculiar requirements or guidelines about the use of SSL in lighting exposition. Suggestion or specifications provided for daylight, lighting levels, irradiance values and colour rendering are independent from source type and technology.

Regarding lighting conservation constraints, this report:

- collects and compares suggestions and requirements described in the most representative and complete documents;
- gives suggestions for SSL lighting based on the colour difference evaluation approach (fading on blue wool).

Regarding colour perception, this report:

- gives suggestions specific for SSL lighting;
- considers the colour rendering capabilities of SSL evaluated on dyes used in works of art.

2 COMPARISON AMONG AVAILABLE DOCUMENTS ON CULTURAL HERITAGE LIGHT INTERACTION

2.1 Conservation suggestions about exposition to light

All analysed documents describe rules to be applied during displays, considering lighting conditions and environmental thermal-humidity constraints. The analysis of these last parameters is out of the scope of this report.

Regarding lighting, the common approach considers the concept of radiant exposure (dose) and maximum irradiance levels allowed (if the document is a standard) or suggested (if the document is a guide). In references [1] [2] [3] [4] [5] [6] [7] [9] the damage due to light is cumulative and depends both on illuminance level and time of exposition. Literature indicates the maximum or acceptable total radiant exposure (annual dose) and irradiance level for visible, UV and IR radiation.

The approach here adopted is based on the idea that all materials have different spectral sensitivity to damage due to radiation, where the spectral sensitivity is the photochemical response of the object divided by the radiance exposure. Theoretically, it would be possible to define such function for every material. Unfortunately, in practical situations, this approach needs be simplified because too many different aspects are involved in the evaluation of spectral responsivity, like:

- the damage is not a linear function of the wavelength (i.e. of the energy of the radiation);
- the damage is clearly related to both photochemical and thermal effects of radiation;
- the potential damage of a source in some cases cannot be expressed as the sum of the potential damage of every single wavelength of the source spectrum (it is not linearly independent);
- the same material can have very different absolute or relative responsivity to light, depending on many variables, including composition, production process, ways of application, age, level and type of pre-existent damage ... ;
- a huge amount of different materials has been used in works of art among thousand of years.

In order to overcome these problems, guidelines and standards group materials in few sensitivity classes, (from three to five, depending on the document), usually with reference also to the BWS scale [10] and usually consider three large band of radiation: visible, UV and IR. For each band, and for each material sensitivity class, in order to limit object's damage, irradiance and dose values are suggested. Damage is usually evaluated as fading, calculated using the CIE colour difference formula [11].

These suggestions are based on the results of different studies carried out comparing the effects of radiation emitted by traditional lighting sources like halogen and fluorescent lamps on reference materials like those adopted in the BWS scale [10].

The most representative documents that will be considered in this report are presented and compared in **Error! Reference source not found..**

These documents use two different approaches to specify the lighting potential damage:

- **Approach A:** the allowed maximum value of energy incident on the artefact (i.e. radiation incident and/or annual total luminous exposure) is suggested;
- **Approach B:** the number of years at a defined irradiance or total luminous exposure level that creates a just perceivable (threshold condition) colour difference (usually $\Delta E=1,6$).

Table 1 Classification of the selected documents and related approaches to specify the lighting potential damage.

Document	Document classification	Approach
CIE157:2002 [1]	Scientific Publication	A and B
UNI 10829:1999 [2]	Italian National Standard (voluntary standard)	A
Italian Decree Law DM10/05/2001 [3]	Italian Law (legally binding – mandatory standard)	A
BSI PAS 198:2011 [4]	BSI Publicly Available Specification	B
Pr-EN16163 [5]	European Standard Draft	A
ANSI IESNA RP-30-96:1996 [6]	USA Recommended Practice	A

All documents classify the cultural heritage materials in different sensitivity to light classes (Table 2): each sensitivity class specifies a recommended maximum value of irradiance and/or annual total luminous exposure and/or the threshold value that give rise to fading, depending on the document approach.

Table 2 Class of sensitivity to light

Document	Classes of sensitivity of materials to light	
CIE157:2002	4 classes: High, Medium, Low responsivity, Irresponsive	8 subclasses referred to Blue Wool categories
UNI 10829:1999	Materials divided in 33 categories	No subclasses
Italian Decree law DM10/05/2001	4 classes: Very High, High, Medium, Very Low responsivity	No subclasses
BSI PAS 198:2011	4 classes: High, Medium, Low responsivity, Irresponsive	No subclasses
Pr-EN16163	4 classes: High, Medium, Low responsivity, Irresponsive	No subclasses
ANSI IESNA RP-30-96:1996	3 classes: High, Moderate, Least susceptible	1 subclass for particularly susceptible/precious materials

CIE 157:2002 is a scientific publication with the objective to correlate total luminous exposure to fading: the values provided are those that give rise to $\Delta E=1,6$ with a radiation with significant UV content (UV content similar to daylight after being filtered by window glass). Also values for radiation without UV are provided, but

the values are clearly indicated as “probable”. This document doesn’t mention the influence of thermo-hygrometric conditions and specific consideration for showcases.

UNI 10829:1999 considers all aspects of the environmental conditions adequate for conservation. The adopted approach suggests maximum allowed values of main environmental parameters for 33 different categories of cultural heritage materials. Because the artefact damage arises as a cumulative and synergic effect of all the environmental parameters, the permitted range of their values are specified. In showcases with internal lighting sources their effect on the other environmental conditions is considered too. The standard also provides indications and limitations about UV and IR content of the emitted radiation of light source and of daylight, if present.

Italian Decree law DM 10/05/2001 is a very wide document completing Italian standard about criteria for museum management, including staff, financial aspects, collections improvement, etc. Environmental conditions and design of lighting installations are considered in details, for example illuminance uniformities are also suggested. The important principle adopted is that all material is considered as sensible to light damage. The law provides also indications about UV and IR content of the incident radiation: for visible and IR, maximum values of the total irradiance in the range 400-4000 nm are provided.

BSI PAS 198:2011 includes suggestions about all environmental parameters. This standard provides the values in years for just noticeable fading to total fade occurring to material of different sensitivity classes at different illuminance values. The values provided, among the same sensitivity class can show variation up to 1 : 20. Definition of upper limits for light exposure is fully delegated to the collecting organizations on the basis of which damage is unacceptable for them within a period of time.

Pr-EN16163 is draft version of an European standard with the aim to define a European common policy about lighting in conservation providing to collecting organizations a reference guide and delegating them the definition of limit values. The document also provides indications about good practice in setting up the lighting design of an exhibition. It is the only document were SSL are considered, but their description is only about technical parameters like: luminous efficacy, life duration, CRI, ... Perceptive or conservative properties are not mentioned.

ANSI IESNA RP-30-96:1996 is an USA Recommended Practice that gives guidelines about the design of lighting system for museum artefacts, including suggestion about the position of luminaires, typical lighting situations ... The document suggests also that UV and IR radiation should be limited by filters, but no limiting values are provided.

A comparison of the main lighting parameters considered by these documents is summarized in Table 3.

Table 3 Comparison of conservative requirements concerning radiation limiting values.

Document	Category of sensitivity	Sub category of sensitivity	Limiting illuminance [lx]	Limiting annual total luminous exposure [klx h/year]	Total luminous exposure before fading [Mlx h]	Limiting UV content [μ W/lm]	Limiting UV irradiance [μ W/cm ²]	Limiting total irradiance range 400-400nm [W/m ²]	Years for just noticeable fading @ 50 lx	Years for just noticeable fading @ 150 lx	Years for just noticeable fading @ 500 lx
CIE157:200 Note1	High	Blue Wool 1	50	15	0,22	Note 1	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.
		Blue Wool 2			0,6	Note 1	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	
		Blue Wool 3			1,5	Note 1	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	
	Medium	Blue Wool 4	50	150	3,5	Note 1	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.
		Blue Wool 5			8	Note 1	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	
		Blue Wool 6			20	Note 1	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	
	Low	Blue Wool 7	200	600	50	Note 1	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.
		Blue Wool 8			120	Note 1	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	
		Blue Wool Over 8			-	Note 1	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	
	Irresponsive		no limit	no limit	-	Note 1	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.
UNI 10829:1999 Note 2	Very High	n.p.	50	200	n.p.	75	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.
	High	n.p.	150	200	n.p.	75	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.
	Medium	n.p.	150	500	n.p.	75	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.
	Low	n.p.	300	no limit	n.p.	75	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.
	Irresponsive	n.p.	no limit	no limit	n.p.	no limit	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.
Italian Decree Law DM10/05/2001 Note 3	Very High	n.p.	50	50	n.p.	10	0,05	1	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.
	High	n.p.	50	150	n.p.	75	0,4	3	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.
	Medium	n.p.	150	500	n.p.	75	1,2	10	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.
	Low	n.p.	>300	no limit	n.p.	75	no limit	no limit	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.

Document	Category of sensitivity	Sub category of sensitivity	Limiting illuminance [lx]	Limiting annual total luminous exposure [klx h/year]	Total luminous exposure before fading [Mlx h]	Limiting UV content [$\mu\text{W}/\text{lm}$]	Limiting UV irradiance [$\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$]	Limiting total irradiance range 400-4000nm [W/m^2]	Years for just noticeable fading @ 50 lx	Years for just noticeable fading @ 150 lx	Years for just noticeable fading @ 500 lx
BSI PAS 198:2011 Note 4	High	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	1,5 - 20	0,5 - 7	0,14 - 2
	Medium	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	20 - 700	7 - 200	2 - 70
	Low	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	300 - 7000	100 - 2000	30 - 700
	Irresponsive	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	no limit	no limit	no limit
Pr-EN16163 Note 5	High	n.p.	n.p.	15	n.p.	75	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.
	Medium	n.p.	n.p.	150	n.p.	75	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.
	Low	n.p.	n.p.	600	n.p.	75	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.
	No sensitivity	n.p.	n.p.	no limit	n.p.	75	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.
ANSI IESNA RP-30-96:1996 Note 6	High	very high	35	n.p.	n.p.	Note 6	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.
		high	50	50	n.p.	Note 6	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.
	Moderate	n.p.	200	480	n.p.	Note 6	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.
	Least	n.p.	no limit	no limit	n.p.	Note 6	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.	n.p.

Note 1:

The values of total luminous exposure before fading are given considering a radiation with a significant UV component, while it is not clear if the limiting of total annual luminous exposure and illuminance values are evaluated considering or not the influence of UV radiation.

Note 2:

For editorial purposes, the maximum allowed values of lighting parameters (Illuminance, UV component and total annual exposure) have been condensed in just 5 different values intervals.

Note 3:

The Italian Decree law suggests also limit values for illuminance uniformity and for total irradiance in the range 400 - 4000 nm.

Note 4:

BSI PAS 198:2011 provides also indication of years for total fade for the same irradiance values, and years for just perceivable and total fade for the same materials classes also at values of 5 klx and 30 klx in daylight conditions.

Note 5:

The analysed version of prEN 16163 is the draft of October 2010

Note 6:

Filters should be used for reducing the UV and IR levels, but no limiting values are provided. With reference to ISO BWS scale, some indications about fading are given and values of time for first perceptible colour change for few pigments at different illuminance levels are specified.

2.1 Suggestions on perceptive aspects in cultural heritage lighting

Regarding the perceptive aspects, the role of good and correct lighting conditions (levels, uniformities, modelling, colour rendering, glare, unwanted reflections) for the enjoyment of a single work of art or a display is widely recognized, but few indications are given.

Full freedom is given to lighting designers in order to enhance the visual experience of visitors. The “appropriate colour” (a term used without definition) should be obtained selecting a lighting source with an appropriate value (not specified) of the CIE Colour Rendering Index (CRI) [12], for the visual task. The modelling aspect important to highlight details or shapes of 3D objects is often not adequately considered.

BSI PAS 198:2011 is the only document where SSL is cited, mainly because it is the most recent one, but no information or indications about objective values of lighting quality parameters for perceptual performance are provided. SSL is considered only for its technical characteristics (i.e. luminous efficacy, life, ...).

2.1 Condition of exposition

Generally, two different conditions of exposition are adopted:

- **Open storage exposition:** the artefacts are exposed in showrooms, not necessary in outdoor conditions;
- **Showcase exposition:** the artefacts are exposed in showcases, with a better control of the exposition conditions.

Showcase exposition should be preferred when the control of environmental parameters is mandatory for the conservation of the artefact. In showcase lighting sources can be put either outside or inside, but special care to unwanted reflection must be taken into account. Sources with thermal impact are usually put outside the showcase or in technical compartment, in order to isolate the exhibition volume from the heat they generate. In some cases optical devices (mirrors, optical fibres, etc.) project the radiation of light sources on the artefact minimising the thermal effects. As a matter of facts, even with moderate illuminance, in a showcase temperature may rise up to 2°C due exclusively to light.

Dedicated standards [7] [9] deeply consider the showcase use in cultural heritage, but they focus especially on environmental parameters to be compliant to and no specific directions are provided for lighting requirements.

3 SSL USE IN CULTURAL HERITAGE EXPOSITIOS

Nowadays SSL is more and more used in museum lighting: the high luminous efficacy, the low IR and UV content and the reduced dimensions, very interesting for special set-up, make this sources very promising and attractive for curators and managers. But a lot of problems are still open: the available standards, as show before, do not make distinction between available sources, nor give special directions on their use. All researches on conservation (based on fading analysis) on which these documents are based have been made with standard sources (incandescent, fluorescent, or simulated daylight): no SSL has been tested. Also, requirements about colour perception are very feeble with only suggestions to use sources with high CRI and favour to incandescent sources or daylighting correlated colour temperature.

Considering recent investigations, some indications specific for SSL can be given especially about conservation constraints and colour perception.

3.1 Conservation aspects: fading with SSL

In this study [13], in order to evaluate the effectiveness of Solid State Lighting (SSL) for museums and art galleries, the colour degradation of Blue Wool Standard (BWS) has been investigated considering the exposure to white LED lamps.

The BWS samples (from 1 to 3 scale) were exposed just above 1 Mlx·h using five types of white LEDs and two traditional museum lamps for a total of seven different light sources. An illuminance level of 10 klx was maintained on BWS during the exposure time: spectral reflectance and colour changes of each sample were regularly measured.

The main goals of the study were to assess:

- LED performance with respect to preventive conservation issues;
- LED performance with respect to colour rendition of works of art
- Applicability of spectral sensitivity of dosimeters, usually adopted in works of art fading studies (i.e. BWS), towards LEDs.

Five types of white LED were selected with different colour temperature but with the same luminescence method for obtaining white light (blue LED + phosphor deposition). Tungsten halogen and linear fluorescent lamps has been selected as reference because they represented the light sources widely used in museum.

The light absorbance of Blue Wool Standard (scale 1, 2, 3) are shown in Figure 1. The characteristics of the seven types of light sources are shown in Table 4 and Figure 2.

Each Blue Wool swatch was placed in an exposure box on top of which one of the seven light sources has been installed. For each lamp the distance from the swatch was adjusted to obtain an illuminance value on the target equal to 10 klx. Figure 3 shows the experimental set-up.

Table 4 Characteristics of light sources used in the experiment

Light source type	Correlated Colour temperature [K]	Colour Rendering Index	UV-A / VIS ratio [$\mu\text{W}/\text{lm}$]	NIR / VIS ratio [mW/lm]
WW-LED1 (warm white LED n. 1)	2580	97	0.58	3.10
WW-LED2 (warm white LED n. 2)	2860	96	0.57	3.15
WW-LED3 (warm white LED n. 3)	3375	91	0.23	2.71
NW-LED (neutral white LED)	3890	97	0.43	2.87
CW-LED (cool white LED)	6980	79	0.15	2.58
WW-TH (halogen lamp)	2860	100	30.30	8.60
CW-CFL (fluorescent lamp)	6500	83	47.31	2.78

Figure 1 The light absorbance of the three scales of the Blue Wool Standard.

Figure 2 The relative spectral distribution of the seven light sources used in the experiment.

Figure 3 The exposure boxes equipped with different white LEDs

The colour degradation was considered only for the scale 1 and 2 of BWS, as for scale 3 colour change didn't exceed the "noticeable fade" $\Delta E = 1.6$ even at the end of the experiment.

Table 6 shows the amount of luminous exposure needs to achieve $\Delta E = 1.6$ in blue scale 1 and 2 towards the light sources used in the experiment. Results are elaborated according to [1] and [11] with illuminant E

(equi-energy) as reference source for ΔE .

Table 5 Luminous exposure needs to obtain a $\Delta E = 1.6$ in BWS S 1 and 2 under different light sources.

Light source type	Luminous exposure to achieve $\Delta E = 1.6$ [klx·h]	
	BWS scale 1	BWS scale 2
WW-LED1 (warm white LED n. 1)	17,0	60,0
WW-LED2 (warm white LED n. 2)	20,0	75,0
WW-LED3 (warm white LED n. 3)	25,5	102,0
NW-LED (neutral white LED)	25,5	93,0
CW-LED (cool white LED)	43,0	145,0
WW-TH (halogen lamp)	14,0	55,0
CW-CFL (fluorescent lamp)	28,0	200,0

Notwithstanding further studies about this test are necessary; some main results can be outlined.

Regarding fading on the BWS scale 1 and 2, $\Delta E = 1.6$ was achieved through different luminous exposure with respect to the seven light sources. This is attributable to the relative spectral distribution of the different light sources and the effective spectral sensitivity of colour degradation of the particular dyes used.

Both blue scale 1 and 2 of BWS resulted more sensitive to light emitted by halogen lamps and LED modules with low CCT ($T_{cp} < 3000$ K) with respect to other light sources. However, none of the BWS sample faded faster under LEDs than under the halogen lamp. These results are partially comparable with [14] and [15].

Because fading arises in very short periods for some pigments and dyes used in works of art [1], [6], in the second part of this study dyed silk samples and a new set of BWS were exposed up to 70 Mlx h using only three of the five white LED lamps (NW-LED, WW-LED1, WW-LED2 type). An illuminance level of 10 klx for each sample was maintained during the aging period and spectral reflectance and colour changes of the samples were regularly measured.

Main results can be outlined as:

- a rank order of light-sensitivity for natural dyes and Blue Wool were assessed through 11 measurement steps of fading rate, achieving a final exposure of 68.5 Mlx h (Table 6);
- according to BWS scale from 1 up to 3, NW-LED module ($T_{cp} = 4000$ K) caused a slower fade with respect to WW-LED1 ($T_{cp} = 2700$ K) and WW-LED2 ($T_{cp} = 3000$ K) modules;
- conversely, most dyes on silk (yellow and red dyes) faded just faster under the NW-LED module, these results are in agreement with very recent studies about fading of yellow dyes [16] [17].

Table 6 Colour change ΔE after 68.5 Mlx·h of luminous exposure for 9 dyes and 3 LES sources of different correlated colour temperature (illuminant E, equi-energy, has been used as reference source for ΔE evaluation).

Dye	White LED lamp		
	WW-LED1 (warm white LED n. 1)	WW-LED2 (warm white LED n. 2)	NW-LED (neutral white LED)
1 - weld	13.4	13.4	13.1
2 - annatto	12.6	13.3	14.4
3 - fustic	18.8	20.6	23.1
4 - indigo	9.0	9.0	9.9
5 - BWS 1	64.7	64.2	61.6
6 - BWS 2	62.0	62.8	60.2
7 - BWS 3	36.0	36.7	34.6
8 - logwood	26.4	27.2	28.5
9 – brazil wood	24.3	24.2	24.7

3.2 Perceptive experience with SSL

In literature, detailed prescriptive references able to provide technical and scientific criteria for the perception of cultural heritage when illuminated with artificial light are not present. Usually, the colour perception of an object is evaluated through the value of the Colour Rendering Index (CRI) of the source [12].

Several documents suggest to choose incandescent light or filtered daylight (to avoid or reduce the UV content of the radiation), or sources (including fluorescent tube) with CRI higher than 85. It is well known that colour-rendering capabilities of a source is calculated on the colour appearance of only 15 different colours, while the chromatic palette of an artefact could be very large. So the CRI value cannot be fully significant in works of arts exposition. Furthermore is known that for the LED sources the value of CRI is not fully dependable.

In order to overcome the limitation due to the limited number of colours in the CIE CRI method, the same mathematical algorithm of [12] has been applied to a larger palette of colours representative of works of arts dyes (49 samples) calculating the colours rendering capabilities of five different LED sources (NW-LED, WW-LED1, WW-LED2, WW-LED3, CW-LED), of a typical incandescent lamp (WW-TH) and of a cold white fluorescent tube (CW- CFL) with the relative spectral distribution of Figure 2.

Table 7 and Table 8 show the Colour Rendering results using:

- the CIE 8 reference samples,
- the CIE 15 reference samples,
- 49 works of arts dyes,
- 64 samples, the CIE 15 reference samples and the 49 works of arts dyes.

Table 7 and Table 8 include the special colour rendering index (R_i) of all samples considered, the general colour rendering index for the specified set of 8 reference colour samples (R_a), the mean results calculated on 15 (R_{all}), 49 (R_{dye}) and 64 (R_{ext}) samples and the Gamut area index (GAI) [18].

Table 7 The colour rendering index of selected LED lights, calculated following CIE method [12] and using CIE standard samples

Light source		NW-LED	WW-LED1	WW-LED2	WW-LED3	CW-LED	WW-TH	CW-CFL
Colour Correlated Temperature	T_{cp} [K]	3890	2580	2860	3375	6980	2860	6500
General CRI on 8 samples	R_a	97	97	96	91	79	100	83
CRI Mean from R1 to R15	R_{all}	96	96	95	90	70	100	76
GAI Mean from R1 to R15	GAI_{REF}	110	114	118	110	90	100	97
Light greyish red	R_1	98	96	95	96	77	100	94
Dark greyish yellow	R_2	97	98	95	92	83	100	89
Strong yellow green	R_3	98	96	98	91	83	100	58
Moderate yellowish green	R_4	98	94	96	94	78	100	87
Light bluish green	R_5	98	96	94	94	77	100	86
Light blue	R_6	95	96	92	87	74	100	78
Light violet	R_7	96	98	97	87	87	100	89
Light reddish purple	R_8	96	99	99	86	69	100	86
Strong red	R_9	94	99	96	79	0	100	44
Strong yellow	R_{10}	97	98	91	86	56	100	48
Strong green	R_{11}	97	91	93	97	73	100	75
Strong blue	R_{12}	87	95	86	74	49	100	60
Human complexion	R_{13}	98	96	94	94	79	100	91
Leaf green	R_{14}	99	97	99	96	90	100	73
Japanese skin	R_{15}	98	98	95	97	75	100	98

Table 8 The colour rendering index of selected LED lights, calculated following CIE method [12] and using selected typical works of arts materials.

Light source		NW-LED	WW-LED1	WW-LED2	WW-LED3	CW-LED	WW-TH	CW-CFL
Colour Correlated Temperature	T_{cp} [K]	3890	2580	2860	3375	6980	2860	6500
CRI mean of 49 dyed samples	R_{dye}	97	96	95	90	70	100	80
CRI mean of 64 samples	R_{ext}	97	97	95	92	73	100	80
GAI mean of 64 samples	GAI_{EXT}	85	51	63	74	89	53	95
Azurite	R16	96	98	95	93	77	100	81
Lapis Lazuli	R17	96	97	95	90	82	100	89
Lapis Lazuli (lead 10%)	R18	96	97	95	90	82	100	89
Ultramarine Blue, dark	R19	91	95	89	80	77	100	77
Prussian Blue	R20	99	99	98	98	94	100	95
Haematite	R21	99	98	97	99	77	100	93
Cadmium Red	R22	90	93	97	70	9	100	16
Lead Tin Yellow, light	R23	95	98	95	85	90	100	79
Naples Yellow, dark	R24	98	97	92	91	59	100	63
Wild Saffron	R25	96	94	89	92	30	100	36
Orpiment, genuine	R26	98	97	91	89	52	100	54
Massicot	R27	98	97	94	92	74	100	77
Red Lead, Minium	R28	96	88	87	95	17	100	60
Realgar	R29	98	97	92	89	61	100	62
Chrome Oxide Green	R30	96	94	97	95	87	100	72
Incarnate, pale	R31	99	99	98	99	92	100	98
Incarnate, medium	R32	99	97	96	98	83	100	98
Incarnate, dark	R33	98	95	92	97	55	100	95
Brazilwood	R34	97	97	97	95	91	100	90
Indigo, Genuine Indian	R35	99	99	99	97	98	100	98
Malachite, natural	R36	97	97	97	93	80	100	89
Bristol Yellow, pale	R37	97	92	87	85	32	100	30
Zinc White	R38	98	100	99	97	96	100	99
White Lead	R39	98	100	99	95	97	100	97
Giallorino	R40	95	98	96	86	92	100	82
Green Earth, German (lead 90%)	R41	98	99	97	92	91	100	86
Green Earth, German (lead 50%)	R42	98	98	96	93	85	100	83
Green Earth, German	R43	99	99	97	96	87	100	88
Iron Oxide Yellow (lead 90%)	R44	99	96	92	90	63	100	62
Iron Oxide Yellow	R45	99	96	92	91	62	100	67
Red Mine Ochre (lead 10%)	R46	98	96	94	98	61	100	92
Raw Umber, from Cyprus	R47	99	98	97	98	87	100	93
Verdigris (lead 90%)	R48	97	99	99	92	94	100	90
Verdigris (lead 50%)	R49	97	96	97	94	82	100	88
Verdigris (lead 10%)	R50	98	98	98	98	89	100	91
Natural Cinnabar (lead 90%)	R51	98	94	91	96	54	100	88
Natural Cinnabar (lead 10%)	R52	98	93	90	97	33	100	85
Madder Lake	R53	96	96	97	90	75	100	80
Violet	R54	94	92	94	84	84	100	81
Smalt, standard grind	R55	98	98	98	96	96	100	97
Cobalt Blue Medium (lead 7%)	R56	99	99	98	97	93	100	93
Cobalt Blue Medium (lead 67%)	R57	97	98	95	92	81	100	82
Cobalt Blue Medium (lead 97%)	R58	96	97	92	90	71	100	75
Cobalt Blue Medium (lead 99%)	R59	96	97	92	92	70	100	75
Cobalt Blue Medium	R60	98	98	97	97	82	100	87
Malachite (lead 90%)	R61	97	97	94	89	85	100	81
Vermilion	R62	98	93	91	96	34	100	91
Incarnate of injured	R63	99	98	95	95	76	100	78
Incarnate of dead	R64	99	98	96	96	81	100	83

From the analysis of the special rendering index for the specified samples, it is clear that the mean value for a set of sample are not suitable for designing lighting installation for works of arts. For example, but this concept can be extended to several other colours, the capabilities of render the red colour of Cold White LED, of a fluorescent source (CW-CFL) with similar CCT and of the reference source is very different. This aspect it is not clearly evident looking at the mean values only, irrespective of the parameter considered (R_a , R_{dye} or R_{ext}).

Because perceptive experiences during an exhibition cannot be standardized and reduced to just a mean value parameter, some suggestion for designing lighting installation can be obtained with *ad hoc* perceptive tests [19].

This experiment is based on a vision test where observer sees, one immediately after the other, two identical polychromatic images into two boxes. The images are illuminated by different light systems that could be LED sources (Figure 4) and traditional lamps with similar CCT (incandescent and fluorescent lamps, Figure 5).

The observers judge the chromatic perception of the scenes shown through an assessment questionnaire. In the questionnaire the light sources are classified as warm (CCT of about 3300 K) and cold (CCT of about 7000 K). Two set of images are used: one has “cold” dominant hues (blue, green, cyan are the used colours), the other has “warm” hues (yellow, red, orange are the used colour).

Then, the results of subjective investigation are analysed statistically and are compared with objective parameters (Table 9). The comparison evaluates if the trend of subjective responses reproduce or not the objective results.

Warm LED compared to incandescent light:

- improves the perception of illumination uniformity, in particular with cold hues;
- for warm hues, doesn't change the colour perception but reduce brightness and saturation;
- for cold hues enhances the colour perception and the brightness, but reduce saturation.

Cold LED compared with fluorescent light:

- improves the perception of illumination uniformity especially with warm hues,
- reduces all colours saturations and brightness perception,
- presents subjective judgements more inconstant than other sources.

By the perceptual point of view, the warm white LEDs have more positive feedback than cool white LEDs and permit to obtain a good illumination of works of art characterized by a predominance of warm hues and an excellent illumination of works of art characterized by a predominance of cold hues. So the warm white LED sources can be of viable substitutes of incandescent lamps.

These suggestions are valid for the illumination of materials characterized by a medium/low photo sensitivity because the perceptive experiment was conducted at an illuminance level of 150/200 lx on the polychromatic

images.

Figure 4 Relative spectral distribution of the LED lights used in subjective test.

Figure 5 Relative spectral distribution of the traditional lamp used in subjective test.

Table 9 Synoptic comparison of subjective and objective of perceptual descriptors.

Subjective descriptors	Objective descriptors	Hues	Warm white LED	Cold white LED
			$T_{cp} = 3000\text{ K}$	$T_{cp} = 6300\text{ K}$
Perceived illuminance Uniformity	$E_{max}/E_{min}; E_{min}/E_{mean}$	Warm	Overestimated	Underestimated
		Cold	Overestimated	Underestimated
Perceived Colour of the light	CCT	Warm	Neutral	Cold
		Cold	Cold	Neutral
Colour Alteration	ΔH^*_{ab}	Warm	Decreased perception	Increased perception
		Cold	Decreased perception	Decreased perception
Colour Saturation	ΔC^*_{ab}	Warm	Decreased perception	Decreased perception
		Cold	Decreased perception	Decreased perception
Colour Brightness	ΔL^*	Warm	Decreased perception	Decreased perception
		Cold	Increased perception	Decreased perception
Dominant Colour	Red is physiologically perceived as dominant	Warm	Physiological coherence	Physiological coherence
	Green is physiologically perceived as dominant	Cold	Physiological incoherence	Physiological coherence
Lighting preference	-	Warm	Not preferred	Not preferred
		Cold	Absolutely preferred	Not preferred
LED source Identification	-	Warm	Recognized	Limited recognized
		Cold	Absolutely recognized	Limited recognized

1. CONCLUSION

Documents (standard or technical report of international organizations) about lighting conditions for cultural heritage:

- have different approaches about the selection of limiting values of photometric parameters;
- adopts different precautionary limits;
- when possible tries to keeping together light and ambient parameters, giving the most careful approach for conservative purposes;

The results of fading experiments show that:

- the same fading level is achieved through different luminous exposure with respect to different light sources;
- fading arises in very short term for some pigments and dyes used in works of art, especially on yellow and red, as also shown in [16] [17];
- more investigations are needed and a more conservative approach must be set up when dyes with high sensitivity to particular wavelengths are lighted with source with relevant radiant flux in these wavelength ranges.

The results of colour perception experiments show that:

- available method for CRI calculation doesn't suit well because the colour rendering of every dyes used in the artefact shall be evaluated independently;
- the mean values of CRI hide the colour rendering capability on special colour, that in same case can be very low;
- CRI values are not in agreement with the results of perceptive experiment, that encourage the use of warm LED especially in cold dyes;
- warm LEDs are preferred for lighting cold hues; they improve uniformity and brightness perception, while cold LEDs are less preferred.

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